

VELEUČILIŠTE

VELIKA GORICA

UNIVERSITY of APPLIED SCIENCES VELIKA GORICA

17th International Conference Crisis Management Days - CMD 2024

CRISIS MANAGEMENT DAYS

GENERATIVE AI APPLICATIONS FOR RISK AND CRISIS MANAGEMENT: THE GOOD, THE BAD, AND THE UGLY

Denis Havlik denis.havlik@ait.ac.at

Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH.

Information (and disinformation) overflow

Illustration. <https://sketchplanations.com/dikw>

- Stakeholders in crisis and catastrophe management (including climate crisis) need to understand the problem at hand and possible solutions.
- Relevant data body is enormous, growing and full of intentional and unintentional misinformation.

For example, relevant climate crisis documents include IPCC report, state and regional plans and reports, EU recommendations, scientific reports, news articles, social media posts...

Knowledge management in a time of crisis

The good

- Knowledge management systems pre-process, summarise and correlate relevant information.
- Stakeholders can act upon digested knowledge without having to read through large amounts of underlying data.

The bad

- „Someone“ has to digest the underlying data and eliminate misinformation. This is a whole lot of work.
 - If done by curators, the process is slow and expensive.
 - If left to data owners, the quality may be lower and data may be missing.

Generative AI systems as knowledge bases?

GPT is NOT a knowledge base!

- Generative Pre-trained transformers can digest large amounts of information
- They can interact with users almost like a human, and produce very convincingly looking text (and more) in response to user's prompts (questions)
- They appear to be knowledge bases, but here is no guarantee that the outputs are correct.

Problems with time, space, and training data

Time

GPT training takes a lot of time and resources. This is why ChatGPT and co. usually aren't „aware“ of any recent events or findings.

Space

GPT systems are bad at spatial reasoning. This is likely to change in the future, but getting the information that's relevant to a specific region will still remain challenging due to deficiencies in underlying data

Underlying data

GPT training requires enormous amounts of data. Chance of contamination with misinformation is high.

Illustration: Training data of GPT- 3

Lie to me! (in a very convincing way)

Hallucinations

Per design, GPT systems will interpolate and extrapolate digested information to generate ist outputs. This leads to „hallucinations“:

- Intrinsic hallucinations - the generated output contradicts the source content.
- Extrinsic hallucinations - the output cannot be verified from the source content (i.e., the source can neither support nor contradict the output).

Missing source problem

When asked to point out the data used to generate an assertion, a GPT system will often invent a source!

- In some cases, GPT will point to an existing document, but a closer inspection will show that the document doesn't support the statement
- In other cases, GPT will even invent documents, e.g. by inventing the title and claiming the authors and journal or conferences that indeed deal with the problem at hand!

Can GPTs be „fixed“?

- Fine-tuning can help with results accuracy and introduce new data
- RAG is akin to letting the GPT look up the answers in a database
- Quality of outputs is very sensitive to exact formulation of the questions
- Reinforced learning can help to weed out misinformation

Should we use GPT systems in knowledge production?

Pro

- GPTs can digest information much faster than humans and at a fraction of price.
- Quality of the answers can, and will be improved
- Capabiliy of GPTs to present information in different forms (e.g. for school children, visually etc) is astonishing.

Contra

- Even the best GPT will ocassionally produce misinformation!
- Ethics of the GPT owners may not be the same as ours

Conclusions

Don't ignore GPT, but don't trust it too much!
OpenAI says it's perfect, but it's really not!

(Inspired by Baby Lasagna „Don't hate yourself, but don't love yourself too much“)

Acknowledgements

- Authors experiences with the generative AI systems have been mostly gathered through development of the knowledge-extraction systems in the scope of the MAIA project, which aims to address the issue of knowledge generation and knowledge
- MAIA project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101056935. Views and opinions expressed are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or CINEA. Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.